

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Serra, F. A. R., Scafuto, I. C., & Serra Vieira, P. (2025). Regulation of Artificial Intelligence: Between the switch and innovation — Is Brazil prepared? *BAR-Brazilian Administration Review*, 22(4), e250015. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-7692bar2025250015>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Serra, F. A. R., Scafuto, I. C., & Serra Vieira, P., & Sátiro, R. M. (2025). Regulation of Artificial Intelligence: Between the switch and innovation — Is Brazil prepared? *Brazilian Administration Review*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17572466>

REVIEWERS:

- Renato Máximo Sátiro (Universidade Federal de Goiás, Brazil)
The other reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Renato Máximo Sátiro
Date review returned: March 06, 2025
Recommendation: Major revision

Comments to the authors

-The topic of artificial intelligence regulation is extremely relevant and timely, as it is directly linked to the evolution of the innovation environment and the balance between control and technological development. As different countries adopt varying regulatory approaches, the way regulations are implemented can significantly impact investment attraction, startup growth, and competitiveness in the AI sector. Therefore, understanding the challenges and opportunities of this regulation is essential for designing policies that foster innovation without compromising fundamental rights and digital security.

-The introduction of the article is succinct and does not delve into fundamental issues for the debate on artificial intelligence regulation in Brazil, failing to explore, for example, the impact of different regulatory approaches on startups and innovation, the country's specific technological infrastructure challenges for AI model development, and the potential conflicts between protecting fundamental rights and fostering an environment conducive to sector growth. Additionally, the introduction does not critically discuss the implications of adopting the European model in the Brazilian context, nor does it adequately contrast the experiences of other emerging economies facing similar challenges in regulating disruptive technologies. These points are essential to contextualizing the relevance of the research and providing the reader with a broader understanding of the issues surrounding AI regulation in Brazil.

-The author mentions in the introduction that there is extensive literature on artificial intelligence regulation but does not clarify how this article contributes to this vast field of study. It is not evident which specific gap is being addressed or what new insight the work offers compared to existing approaches. The absence of this justification raises the question: why do we need another article on this topic? To establish its academic relevance, the study should clearly indicate where it fits within the debate and what sets it apart from previous research.

-Section 2, which addresses the fundamentals of artificial intelligence regulation, provides a broad overview of the topic but lacks critical depth and a clearer stance on the specific challenges of regulation in the Brazilian context. Although it mentions the complexity of regulation and references international approaches, the section is limited to describing concepts without exploring their practical implications or potential contradictions between regulatory security and the stimulation of innovation. Additionally, the application of Lawrence Lessig's model could have been more detailed concerning Brazil, discussing, for example, whether the country has the institutional structure to adequately balance laws, market forces, architecture, and social norms in AI development. Finally, the section could have included a greater contrast between different regulatory perspectives, highlighting not only their principles but also their concrete consequences for technology adoption and competitiveness. How has each country and market practically positioned itself in response to various regulatory impulses?

-At some point while reading Section 2, I expected institutional theory to be mentioned, since, ultimately, artificial intelligence regulation is embedded within the institutional environment that influences the evolution (or stagnation) of technology. Institutionalism, with authors such as Douglass North, Paul DiMaggio, and Walter Powell, provides a crucial theoretical framework for understanding how formal and informal rules shape the adoption and development of new technologies. Regulatory approaches do not exist in a vacuum but rather within an institutional context that defines incentives, limitations, and the trajectory of innovation. The absence of this discussion weakens the analysis, as it prevents a deeper understanding of the structural factors that can either facilitate or hinder AI regulation and advancement in Brazil. - Table 2 presents a classification of the references used on artificial intelligence regulation but does not clarify the criteria adopted for selecting these sources. It is not evident why certain documents, academic articles, and institutional reports were chosen over others, nor whether there was a methodological criterion to ensure a diversity of perspectives or relevance to the debate. Additionally, the table groups different types of sources without explaining the weight each category had in shaping the article's argumentation, which compromises the transparency and consistency of the literature review. The lack of justification for these choices limits the reader's ability to assess the robustness of the theoretical foundation used and raises concerns about potential biases in the approach to the topic.

-Section 3, which discusses the landscape of artificial intelligence regulation in Brazil, provides a general overview of the developing legislation but lacks a deeper critical analysis of the challenges and practical implications of the chosen model. Although it mentions the influence of the European model in shaping Bill 2338/2023, it does not sufficiently question whether this choice is appropriate for the Brazilian reality, considering factors such as institutional capacity for oversight, the maturity level of the AI sector in the country, and the impacts on startups and emerging companies. Furthermore, the section could have explored more comparisons with other emerging economies, such as India and Latin American countries, which undeniably share social, economic, and, to some extent, institutional contexts that are more comparable to Brazil's scenario. Evaluating different regulatory approaches and their outcomes in these countries would have added depth to the discussion. The lack of a more detailed examination of the incentives needed to balance regulation and innovation leaves the analysis incomplete, making the section more descriptive than analytical.

-The methodology presents significant limitations, particularly regarding the lack of detail on how the analyzed sources were selected. There is no clarity on the criteria used to choose the legislative documents, reports, and articles included in the research, nor whether a strategy was employed to ensure a diversity of perspectives or to mitigate bias in the analysis. This lack of transparency compromises the study's reproducibility and the reliability of its conclusions. Furthermore, the procedure for analyzing these sources was not sufficiently described, leaving doubts about how the data were extracted, organized, and interpreted. Without greater methodological detail, the validity of the inferences drawn throughout the article is weakened.

-Another critical point is that the analysis of Bill 2338/2023 could have been conducted in a more technical manner, using widely recognized methods for evaluating public policies. One example is Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA), a methodology adopted in various countries to assess the potential effects of new regulations. RIA enables the identification of costs, benefits, and impacts on different societal stakeholders before the implementation of regulations, ensuring greater predictability and effectiveness. Additionally, a comparative analysis based on Economic Regulation Theory could have been employed to examine how regulation affects incentives, entry barriers, and the balance between state control and innovation. These approaches would make the evaluation more structured and well-founded, preventing generalizations or superficial interpretations regarding the suitability of the proposed regulation.

-The conclusion section reinforces the article's main findings but could be more assertive in defining the study's specific contribution to the debate on artificial intelligence regulation. While it effectively summarizes the differences between regulatory models and the challenges Brazil faces in adopting the European approach, it does not go further in offering

practical recommendations or more concrete policy implications. Additionally, there is a lack of reflections on the next steps for research, such as potential empirical studies or the application of more rigorous methodologies to assess the regulatory impacts on the AI sector. - Section 7, which focuses on the discussion, presents an interesting comparative analysis of different regulatory models but lacks a deeper reflection on the institutional environment and its influence on technological innovation. Artificial intelligence regulation does not occur in isolation but within an institutional context that includes factors such as governance, legal security, economic incentives, and the state's enforcement capacity. The absence of a discussion on how Brazil's institutional environment may impact the implementation of the European model and AI sector innovation leaves the analysis incomplete. Scholars like Douglass North and Richard Scott argue that formal and informal institutions are crucial determinants of technological evolution, and incorporating this perspective could enrich the discussion by exploring the structural barriers that may hinder AI development in Brazil.

-Additionally, the section focuses primarily on comparisons between different countries' regulatory models but does not deeply discuss how these models concretely impact the innovation ecosystem. For example, the article mentions that more flexible regulations favor startups and attract investments, but it does not provide empirical evidence or specific examples of countries that have successfully implemented this approach. The inclusion of quantitative data on investments, startup growth, or AI development in different regulatory contexts would strengthen the argument, making the analysis more robust and grounded in measurable outcomes.

-Another aspect that could be improved is the implementation challenge. The section acknowledges the difficulties Brazil faces in adopting the European model but does not detail the main institutional and operational bottlenecks in applying this regulation. Issues such as enforcement challenges, lack of technological infrastructure, and the impact on small and medium-sized enterprises are crucial and could have been explored in greater depth. Furthermore, there is no reflection on possible solutions or alternative approaches to balance innovation and regulatory control, which would make the section more propositional rather than merely descriptive.

-Finally, the discussion could have engaged more critically with the academic literature on regulation and innovation, incorporating concepts such as "responsive regulation" or "adaptive regulation," which suggest more flexible approaches for rapidly evolving sectors. Without this deeper exploration, the section comes across as overly descriptive and does not advance to a more analytical level regarding the consequences of different regulatory choices.

-Section 8, which presents the final considerations, fulfills its role in summarizing the study's main findings but could have been more assertive in highlighting the article's specific contributions to the academic and regulatory debate. While it reinforces the need to adapt the European model to the Brazilian reality, the conclusion does not clearly specify which gaps in the existing literature the study addresses or how its findings can be applied to future public policy formulations. Additionally, the section mentions the importance of a hybrid model to balance regulation and innovation but does not go further in proposing a more concrete regulatory framework for Brazil, leaving the recommendation at a generic level. Another limitation is the lack of structured suggestions for future research, which could include empirical analyses on regulatory impacts on AI adoption in Brazil, comparative studies with other emerging economies, or the application of quantitative methodologies to assess regulatory risks and benefits. Thus, while the section coherently concludes the article, it could have been more proactive and better grounded in the literature on innovation and regulatory governance to strengthen its contribution to the field. .

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: No

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: No

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state "none" if this is not applicable):.

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Average

Originality: Average

Overall: Average

Authors' Response

Dear Prof. Ricardo Limongi

Editor of Brazilian Administration Review

We are grateful for the opportunity to revise our manuscript and for the insightful and detailed comments provided by the reviewers. We took all criticisms seriously and undertook a comprehensive revision of the paper, which includes not only conceptual and methodological enhancements but also improved articulation of theoretical foundations and analytical depth. We have also prepared a supplementary file to address specific issues of transparency and replicability, as suggested.

The revised manuscript seeks to respond to the major points raised concerning the lack of theoretical anchoring, limited critical comparative analysis, insufficient methodological detail, and underdeveloped discussion of Brazil's institutional specificities. We believe that the new version reflects substantial improvement and addresses all concerns raised.

Below, we provide a detailed response to each reviewer, structured point-by-point. All changes in the manuscript are marked and referenced.

Reviewer 1

We thank Reviewer 1 for the thoughtful review and valuable suggestions. We address each concern below.

1. The introduction is succinct and does not delve into fundamental issues for the debate on AI regulation in Brazil, such as the impact on startups, infrastructure limitations, and conflicts between fundamental rights and innovation.

Response:

We have expanded the introduction (Section 1) to integrate the specific challenges facing Brazil, including its limited technological infrastructure, the fragile startup ecosystem, and institutional asymmetries in oversight. These concerns are now explicitly framed within the broader research question and linked to the global regulatory landscape. Furthermore, we added references to the potential conflicts between safeguarding fundamental rights and fostering innovation, a tension particularly visible in Brazil's legislative proposals. A new paragraph has also been inserted to highlight the regulatory transplantation risks Brazil faces by mimicking EU norms without the same institutional support structures.

2. The article fails to clearly state its academic contribution and what specific gap it addresses in the literature.

Response:

We agree with this important observation. In response, we clarified the research gap at the end of Section 1 and again in the revised Conclusion. We now emphasize that the paper contributes to the literature by combining Lessig's framework with institutional theory to evaluate the regulatory trajectories of emerging economies. Our work identifies the problem of "regulatory isomorphism" (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983) and explores its effects on implementation and innovation outcomes. This combination has not been systematically applied to AI regulation in Brazil or similar countries to date.

Additionally, the revised version now includes a dedicated paragraph in Section 5 highlighting the theoretical contribution, specifically, how Brazil exemplifies the risks of legal transplantation and mimetic isomorphism, and practical implications in terms of adaptive regulatory design.

3. Section 2 lacks critical depth regarding Brazil's regulatory context and does not adequately explore contradictions between security and innovation.

Response:

We completely revised Section 2 to address this concern. Subsection 2.1 now integrates institutional theory (North, 1990; DiMaggio & Powell, 1983) to better account for the contextual limits of regulation in Brazil. We also enhanced our discussion of Lessig's model with critical attention to how each vector interacts under limited enforcement capacity. The Brazilian case is treated as a hybrid configuration shaped by political volatility, fragmented governance, and normative diffusion. This expanded framing allows us to explore contradictions between security and innovation explicitly.

4. The application of Lessig's model to Brazil is superficial. It should discuss whether the country has the institutional structure to balance laws, markets, architecture, and norms.

Response:

We developed a new country-specific subsection in the Results (Section 4.10), where Lessig's four vectors are systematically applied to the Brazilian case. We critically assess Brazil's regulatory instruments, infrastructure, market maturity, and cultural norms, and then provide a critical synthesis. Moreover, Section 5.2 contrasts Brazil's position with that of other emerging markets, focusing on institutional limitations and how these affect the regulatory model's coherence.

5. Institutional theory should be incorporated, as AI regulation occurs within institutional environments.

Response:

We thank the reviewer for highlighting this omission. As noted above, institutional theory now plays a central role in the revised theoretical framework (Section 2.1). We apply North's (1990) distinction between formal and informal rules and use DiMaggio and Powell's concept of institutional isomorphism to explain Brazil's adoption of the European model. We also cite Bradford's (2020) "Brussels Effect" to show how EU norms shape legislation in weaker institutional contexts.

6. Table 2 (now SP1) lacks justification for source selection and categorization.

Response:

We addressed this in our Supplementary File A, which includes: A five-step protocol for document selection and validation; Inclusion/exclusion criteria; Clear categorization of sources (governmental, academic, institutional); Justification for the analytical weighting given to each jurisdiction.

Table SP1 lists 52 documents across 8 countries, clearly identifying source type, institutional origin, and analytical relevance.

7. Section 3 lacks a critical analysis of Bill 2338/2023 and the choice to follow the EU model.

Response:

We revised Section 4.2 entirely to apply a Regulatory Impact Assessment (RIA) framework to Bill 2338/2023. We assess stakeholder impacts, implementation feasibility, and institutional burdens. We also incorporate insights from Economic Regulation Theory to explore how the proposal may affect innovation incentives, startup costs, and administrative efficiency.

8. The methodology lacks transparency, particularly regarding source selection and analysis procedures.

Response:

As requested, we now provide full methodological transparency in the Supplementary File, including: Document selection strategy; Coding categories and justification (using MAXQDA); Analytical procedure aligned with Lessig's model and regulatory theory.

These changes aim to ensure the study is replicable and rigorous.

9. The article does not explore implementation challenges in sufficient depth.

Response:

This concern is now addressed in Section 5.2 and 5.3. We identify Brazil's primary bottlenecks in terms of institutional capacity, enforcement mechanisms, lack of sectoral articulation, and digital infrastructure gaps. We also propose adaptive alternatives drawn from Chile and the UK.

10. The conclusion is not assertive in its contributions or practical implications.

Response:

We revised the Conclusion (Section 6) to explicitly outline the article's contributions, both theoretical and applied. We now propose a hybrid, adaptive regulatory model for Brazil and recommend strengthening interinstitutional collaboration and flexible oversight mechanisms. Limitations and suggestions for future research are also included.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Renato Máximo Sátiro

Date review returned: July 24, 2025

Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

O autor atendeu integralmente à maioria dos pontos críticos que foram levantados, os quais detalharei abaixo. Apenas o item sobre inclusão de dados quantitativos ou evidências empíricas concretas permanece parcialmente resolvido. O artigo demonstra grande amadurecimento teórico, metodológico e analítico, com excelente incorporação das recomendações.

-A introdução foi significativamente ampliada, com menção clara aos desafios do Brasil relacionados à infraestrutura, startups, capacidade institucional e riscos de transposição normativa do modelo europeu. A tensão entre inovação e direitos também está explícita.

-O artigo agora deixa claro que contribui ao combinar o modelo de Lessig com teoria institucional para analisar o isomorfismo regulatório. Essa contribuição é destacada na introdução, seção teórica e conclusão. - A Seção 2 foi reformulada e ganhou densidade analítica com destaque para a aplicação da teoria institucional e os limites estruturais do país. A seção 2.1 mostra bem as contradições entre controle regulatório e estímulo à inovação.

-Foi criada uma nova subseção com aplicação detalhada do modelo de Lessig ao Brasil, considerando os quatro vetores (lei, mercado, arquitetura e normas sociais) de forma crítica e contextualizada. - A seção 2.1 introduz com clareza a distinção entre regras formais e informais (North) e o conceito de isomorfismo institucional (DiMaggio & Powell), bem como os riscos da adoção simbólica de modelos estrangeiros.

-O artigo agora utiliza a metodologia de Análise de Impacto Regulatório (RIA) para avaliar o PL 2338/2023, considerando efeitos práticos, custos, e incentivos, além de discutir alternativas mais adequadas à realidade brasileira.

-O material suplementar detalha o processo de coleta e seleção documental, codificação (com uso do MAXQDA), critérios analíticos e estrutura comparativa. A metodologia agora é replicável e traz um maior detalhamento dos procedimentos.

-No texto agora há discussões sobre gargalos institucionais do Brasil, como fragmentação regulatória, baixa capacidade de enforcement e limitações técnicas. Também propõem soluções baseadas em experiências do Chile e Reino Unido.

-A nova conclusão sintetiza bem os achados, propõe um modelo híbrido adaptativo, recomenda medidas práticas (ex: sandboxes, colaboração interinstitucional) e sugere caminhos para futuras pesquisas. - As seções finais incorporam reflexões estruturadas sobre o papel das instituições brasileiras, com base em North, Scott, DiMaggio e Powell. A relação entre ambiente institucional e inovação está bem desenvolvida. - Embora o artigo tenha fortalecido a análise comparativa, ainda carece de dados quantitativos sobre impacto regulatório (ex: investimentos ou crescimento de startups por país). A crítica permanece válida, mas o avanço foi significativo em termos qualitativos.

-Os principais gargalos institucionais foram bem discutidos. O artigo traz propostas de regulação adaptativa e aprendizado regulatório, com exemplos concretos de países semelhantes.

-O conceito de “regulação adaptativa” aparece expresso no texto, com base em estudos de sandbox e experimentação regulatória. O artigo articula essa abordagem com as capacidades institucionais do Brasil.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable):

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Average

Originality: Good

Overall: Good

Authors' Response

Dear Prof. Ricardo Limongi,

We thank you for the opportunity to revise our manuscript "Regulation of Artificial Intelligence: Between the Switch and Innovation -- Is Brazil prepared?" (Manuscript ID BAR-2025-0015.R1). We are pleased to resubmit it with substantial revisions addressing the key concern raised regarding the inclusion of quantitative data and concrete empirical evidence.

Following your guidance to focus on Reviewer 1's recommendations, we have incorporated quantitative data throughout the manuscript while maintaining the theoretical and analytical rigor that Reviewer 2 appreciated. The revisions strengthen the empirical foundation of our comparative analysis.

We believe these revisions have substantially strengthened the manuscript and look forward to your decision.

Yours sincerely,

(The authors)

RESPONSES TO REVIEWER 1 COMMENTS

We deeply appreciate Reviewer 1's thorough evaluation and positive assessment of our theoretical and methodological improvements. We are pleased that the reviewer acknowledged our paper shows "great theoretical, methodological and analytical maturity" and that we have "fully addressed most critical points." We have now addressed the remaining concern.

Point 1. "Although the article has strengthened comparative analysis, it still lacks quantitative data on regulatory impact (e.g., investments or startup growth by country). The criticism remains valid, but the qualitative advancement was significant."

Response: We have comprehensively addressed this concern by incorporating quantitative data and concrete empirical evidence throughout the manuscript. In Section 6.5, we added a substantial paragraph presenting Brazilian market data, including the market size growing from \$3 billion in 2023 to a projected \$49.2 billion by 2030, the Brazilian AI Plan investment allocation of 23.03 billion reais (approximately \$4 billion for 2024-2028), and Brazil's regional position as host to the majority of Latin America's AI startups while representing only 5.6% of the global market.

Section 6.7 now includes two comprehensive paragraphs with comparative investment data demonstrating the quantitative impact of regulatory approaches. We present data showing the US attracted \$328.5 billion between 2019-2023 with 65.94% growth in 2023 alone, while China saw investments decelerate to \$15.1 billion in 2023, representing a significant reduction since 2019. The UK captured \$25.5 billion over the five-year period. We also incorporated startup formation statistics showing the US created 4,633 AI startups between 2013-2022, including 524 in 2022 alone, and global funding distribution data revealing that 76% of worldwide AI funding goes to countries with flexible regulation compared to \$8 billion received by Europe with its stricter framework.

We enhanced Section 7 (Discussion) with a quantitative analysis paragraph that reinforces the correlation between regulatory flexibility and investment attraction, specifically comparing the US capture of 76% of global AI funding in 2024, totaling \$67.9 billion in 2023 alone, against Brazil's projected \$4 billion through 2028. Table 3 was expanded with a new "AI Investment (2023)" column providing concrete figures for all compared countries, directly addressing the reviewer's request for quantitative regulatory impact data.

These additions are supported by seven new authoritative references including AIPRM (2024), CB Insights (2025), UNCTAD (2024), Grand View Research (2024), TechCrunch (2025), Edge Delta (2024), and AI Asia Pacific Institute (2025), ensuring all quantitative claims are properly substantiated with current, reliable sources.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 3

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Renato Máximo Sátiro
Date review returned: August 18, 2025
Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the authors

O avaliador considera que, nesta versão, os pontos solicitados foram devidamente incorporados ao texto. Os números relativos ao fenômeno (movimentação de capitais, investimentos no setor, impacto econômico) foram trazidos ao texto de forma satisfatória, com fontes confiáveis e atuais.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable): Nenhum.

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Good

Originality: Excelent

Overall: Good

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

There is no authors' response for this round.